

Supplemental Material to "Integrating Fiber-Optic Seismic Arrays into Earthquake Early Warning Systems with the dEPIC Framework"

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replay_events

ID	latitude	longitude	depth	magnitude	origin_time	description
nc73799091	37.312	-121.672	8.4	5.1	2022-10-25 18:42:02	M 5.1 - 15km ESE of Alum Rock, CA
nc73866925	36.801	-121.323	10.2	4.4	2023-04-04 22:23:17	M 4.4 - 1km NNW of Tres Pinos, CA
nc75068161	36.912	-121.653	6.9	4.2	2024-09-29 9:47:33	M 4.2 - 3 km of Aromas, CA
nc73774300	36.549	-121.097	1.6	4.0	2022-09-01 13:36:22	M 4.0 - 5km ENE of Pinnacles, CA
nc75137161	36.695	-121.325	4.7	3.9	2025-02-22 10:31:25	M 3.9 - 11 km SSW of Tres Pinos, CA
nc73827436	36.595	-121.206	7.7	3.9	2023-01-01 6:49:10	M 3.9 - 9km NW of Pinnacles, CA
nc73856426	36.594	-121.201	9.3	3.8	2023-03-07 14:33:12	M 3.8 - 9km NW of Pinnacles, CA
nc75106461	36.601	-121.231	7.6	3.6	2024-12-22 1:44:44	M 3.6 - 11 km NW of Pinnacles, CA
nc73918291	37.256	-121.632	5.9	3.6	2023-07-30 13:49:04	M 3.6 - 14 km N of Morgan Hill, CA
nc73836266	37.109	-121.517	5.7	3.6	2023-01-23 13:58:02	M 3.6 - 9km ENE of San Martin, CA
nc73834041	36.810	-121.531	5.3	3.6	2023-01-19 17:15:55	M 3.6 - 4km S of San Juan Bautista, CA
nc73814941	37.326	-121.688	8.2	3.6	2022-12-05 23:13:16	M 3.6 - 13km ESE of Alum Rock, CA
nc73799186	37.311	-121.675	8.1	3.5	2022-10-25 22:08:37	M 3.5 - 15km E of Seven Trees, CA
nc73987616	36.421	-121.927	7.1	2.9	2024-01-11 0:46:52	M 2.9 - 13 km N of Point Sur, CA
nc73797331	36.913	-122.160	8.1	2.4	2022-10-21 14:29:11	M 2.4 - 13km WSW of Santa Cruz, CA
nc75153077	36.838	-122.129	10.5	2.3	2025-03-22 5:26:54	M 2.3 - 17 km SW of Santa Cruz, CA
nc73974081	36.603	-122.046	7.5	2.3	2023-12-10 7:39:08	M 2.3 - 9 km WNW of Del Monte Forest, CA
nc75043822	36.916	-122.169	10.5	2.1	2024-08-05 14:28:43	M 2.1 - 14 km WSW of Santa Cruz, CA
nc73804755	36.991	-122.240	1.1	2.1	2022-11-13 19:16:32	M 2.1 - 10km SW of Bonny Doon, CA
nc75058341	36.697	-122.080	11.5	2.0	2024-09-07 0:22:54	M 2.0 - 17 km NW of Pacific Grove, CA
nc73774875	36.792	-121.912	10.9	2.0	2022-09-03 4:00:06	M 2.0 - 11km W of Moss Landing, CA

Figure S1: Table of replay events.

Figure S2: Magnitude estimation evolution for all replay events.

Figure S3: Full-day dEPIC real-time results for 08 October 2025. Accepted (orange circles) and rejected (red crosses) dEPIC solutions with magnitude estimates and median absolute deviation values. Catalog events (blue circles) are shown with magnitude uncertainties. Green bars indicate event distances from the DAS array. Solutions with maximum magnitude estimates associated with catalog events are shown with location errors (purple dots).

Figure S4: (a) Observed additional warning time from replays; (b) Estimated additional warning time as defined in Gou et al., 2025.

Figure S5: Saturation magnitude as a function of hypocentral distance and channel number, estimated from the theoretical maximum strain rate measurable with the SeaFOAM DAS array configuration. The upper panel shows results for P waves and the lower panel for S waves, based on the calibrated empirical magnitude – peak strain-rate relationship in Gou et al., 2025. The estimation is based on a configuration with a 20.4-m gauge length and a 200-Hz repetition rate.

Figure S6: Full-day dEPIC real-time results for 10 October 2025. Same legend as in Figure S3, with black dashed lines indicating two M7+ teleseismic events.

Figure S7: Evaluation of different thresholds for the two location metrics to assess the trade-off between alert timeliness and location accuracy. The adopted thresholds (prominence = 1.15 and distribution = 0.80, shown as red crosses) achieve a balanced performance and have proven effective in real-time tests.

Figure S8: Daily 10-min average latency data from real-time operation. The average latency between DAS interrogator and the dEPIC processor is around 0.53s.

1 REFERENCES

1. Gou, Y., Allen, R. M., Zhu, W., Taira, T. and Chen, L.-W. Leveraging submarine DAS arrays for offshore earthquake early warning: A case study in monterey bay, California. *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.* 115, 516–532 (2025).